

Hydrophobicity of α -crystallin and its relationship with chaperone activity-bis-ANS binding study

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Abstract : α -Crystallin is the major structural protein of eye lens of vertebrates. The temperature driven exposure of hydrophobic surfaces in α -crystallin was accompanied by enhancement in chaperone activity. We have used bis-ANS and ANS binding to understand some structural changes of thermally perturbed α -crystallin and get an insight into chaperone activity of thermally treated α -crystallin. The constancy of the emission maxima of bis-ANS bound to pre-incubated α_L -crystallin added before or after heating indicated that only number of exposed sites varied, but their environment remained unchanged. Initially bis-ANS was bound to the pocket quite loosely and with time it was tightly grabbed into the pocket. Furthermore our results showed that although bis-ANS binding to α_L -crystallin was a relatively slow process and took few hours to reach equilibrium, the structural changes that occurred to α_L -crystallin on cooling a solution after heating above 60 °C was attained immediately. Our insulin assay at 37 °C revealed that prior binding of bis-ANS to α_A - and α_B -crystallin slightly suppressed its chaperone activity. This indicated that substrate bound to the same hydrophobic sites where bis-ANS was bound. At the condition of thermal assay, the interaction between ANS/bis-ANS and α_L -crystallin may be very flexible and hence presence of ANS or bis-ANS had very little effect on the chaperone activity of α_L -crystallin.

Keywords : α -Crystallin, molecular chaperone, bis-ANS, thermal aggregation, β -crystallin, hydrophobicity, binding sites, dissociation constant.

Introduction

α -, β - and γ -crystallins are the main constituents of the eye lens fiber cells¹. Among the crystallins, α -crystallin is the major protein having average molecular mass of 800 kDa². α -Crystallin contains two types of subunits α_A and α_B with molecular masses 19,832 and 20,079 kDa respectively². α -Crystallin has very high sequence homology to small heat shock proteins³⁻⁵. The presence of α -crystallin subunits in other organs such as brain, heart, kidney, spleen, thymus etc. has also been established⁶⁻⁹. α -Crystallin acts as a chaperone by prevention of aggregation of heat-denatured proteins¹⁰⁻¹⁵, UV-irradiated proteins^{10,16} and chemically denatured proteins¹⁷. It has

been demonstrated that α -crystallin form complex with denatured proteins^{15,18}.

Proteins contain both hydrophilic and hydrophobic side chain residues. Individual protein has its own folding pattern in which they arrange hydrophobic residues in such a way that some hydrophobic residues may be buried in the interior and others may be exposed at the surface. The several properties of protein like conformation, solubility, ligand binding, aggregation etc. are largely determined by hydrophobic interactions. Relationship between the hydrophobicity and physico-chemical properties of proteins has been the subject of interest¹⁹⁻²¹. Several experiments have been done for determination of hydrophobicity

of protein. One of these methods is fluorescent probe method²². Stryer showed that the quantum yield of 1-anilinonaphthalene-8-sulfonic acid (ANS) increased after binding to the hydrophobic sites of proteins whereas it remained nonfluorescent in aqueous solution. Since then ANS is used as an external fluorescent probe²³.

The mechanism of chaperone activity is still unknown. It was believed that during chaperone action, substrate proteins were bound through the hydrophobic sites of α -crystallin¹⁴. There appeared to be a direct correlation between the surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity of α -crystallin²⁴⁻²⁷. The chaperone activity of α -crystallin was enhanced with increase of temperature^{25,28-31}. It was seen that thermal assay required less α -crystallin for protection than non-thermal assay^{12,17}. The conformational change of α -crystallin due to heating lacked reversibility²⁵. In order to find correlation between chaperone activity and physico-chemical properties, we have studied the hydrophobicity of α -crystallin. We have investigated the nature of exposed hydrophobic sites at elevated temperature. We have calculated the number of binding sites and dissociation constant of bis-ANS binding in case of native and heat pre-treated α_L -crystallin. In the present study, we have also tried to see whether the hydrophobic sites exposed on heating, come back to the original conformation over an extended period of time. Lastly, we have performed the thermal and non-thermal assay of chaperone activity with bis-ANS and ANS bound α_L -crystallin.

Experimental

Materials :

All buffer salts and DTT were obtained from SRL. Bis-ANS and ANS were purchased from Molecular Probes, USA. Insulin was obtained from Sigma.

Isolation and purification of α_L -crystallin :

Bovine eye lenses were obtained from a local slaughter house and stored at -80 °C until use. The lenses were homogenized in 10 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.5, containing 0.1 M NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.02%

NaN₃ and 0.5 mM DTT and centrifuged at 5000 x g at 4 °C for 20 min. The supernatant were fractionated by gel filtration on a column of Sephacryl S-300 HR to get the fraction corresponding to α_H -, α_L -, β_H -, β_L - and γ -crystallin. To get purified α_L -crystallin, pooled fractions was loaded on a Sephacryl S-400 HR column. Then it was dialyzed against 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 and stored at -20 °C until required.

Isolation and purification of β_L -crystallin :

To obtain purified β_L -crystallin, pooled fraction from Sephacryl S-300 chromatography was loaded on a Sephacryl S-200 HR column. Then it was dialyzed against 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 and stored at -20 °C until required.

Recombinant preparation of αA - and αB -crystallin :

Plasmid DNA of human αA -crystallin in pAED4 vector was a gift from Dr. W. W. de Jong of Katholic University, The Netherlands. Plasmid for human αB -crystallin in pET20b+ expression vector was provided as a gift by Dr. J. Horwitz of Jules Stein Eye Institute, Los Angeles, CA, USA. For over expression, both the plasmids were separately introduced into *Escherichia coli* strain BL21-DE3. Cultures were grown in LB medium at 37 °C with IPTG induction. Cells were centrifuged, subjected to freeze-thaw treatment and then extracted with DNase and lysozyme. Proteins were dialyzed in 20 mM Tris buffer, pH 7.2 containing 0.5 mM EDTA and 0.5 mM DTT (buffer-A) and the precipitate removed by centrifugation. Protein solutions were concentrated in Amicon stirred cell using 100 kDa cut off membrane. Proteins solutions were applied to DEAE anion exchange column and eluted with linear 0–0.5 M NaCl gradients. Pooled αA - and αB -crystallin fractions were then applied to Sephacryl S-300 HR size exclusion column (1.5 cm \times 95 cm) and eluted with buffer-A containing 0.1 M NaCl. Pooled main fractions were concentrated and dialyzed against buffer-A or 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, containing 0.5 mM DTT (buffer-B) and stored in aliquots at -70 °C. SDS-PAGE of both αA - and

α B-crystallin showed single band around 20 kDa. Concentration of intact recombinant proteins in solution was determined spectrophotometrically by measuring absorbance at 280 nm using extinction coefficients of $0.83 \text{ (mg/ml)}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $0.95 \text{ (mg/ml)}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ for α A- and α B-crystallin respectively³².

Bis-ANS binding studies :

(a) Fluorimetric titration :

α_L -Crystallin of 0.1 mg/ml (2 ml) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, was taken in a fluorescence cuvette. This solution was titrated with concentrated bis-ANS solution (744 μ M), adding small aliquots at a time. After each addition, the solution was stirred magnetically for 1 min and bis-ANS fluorescence spectrum was recorded between 450–550 nm using excitation wavelength of 390 nm in a Hitachi F4500 spectrofluorimeter. Both the excitation and emission slits were fixed at 2.5 nm each. Fluorescence intensity at 490 nm was measured from each spectrum and readings were corrected for buffer blanks and dilution. A reverse titration was performed where bis-ANS concentration was kept fixed at 1 μ M and the protein concentration varied between 0 and 32 μ M. Here also the fluorescence intensity at 490 nm was recorded and a plot of 1/fluorescence intensity vs 1/protein concentration was generated³³.

Experiments were also done with α_L -crystallin which was heat treated prior to the bis-ANS titration. This was referred to as “pre-heated α_L -crystallin”. To do this, α_L -crystallin of 1 mg/ml was heated at 90 °C for 30 min and cooled to room temperature for 1 h. From this 0.1 mg/ml protein solution was prepared for titration with bis-ANS. For reverse titration, α_L -crystallin solution (1 mg/ml) was heated at 90 °C, cooled and then concentrated in a microcon. 1 μ M bis-ANS solution (2 ml) was titrated with this concentrated protein solution whose final concentration varied from 0–13 μ M. Similar experiments were performed with pre-heated α_L -crystallin varying incubation time for cooling such as 2 h, 8 h and 24 h.

Bis-ANS binding study was also performed for

recombinant human α A- and α B-crystallin. α A-Crystallin of 0.05 mg/ml in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 was titrated with bis-ANS varying concentration from 0–16 μ M. α A-Crystallin of same concentration was incubated at 37 °C and 55 °C for 1 h and cooled to room temperature for 1 h. These pre-heated protein solutions were titrated with bis-ANS. Reverse titration was also done for all the cases in the same way as described in the literature³³. We have done the similar experiments for α B-crystallin as in the case of α A-crystallin.

(b) Equilibrium incubation :

Individual solutions of α_L -crystallin of 0.1 mg/ml in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 were mixed with bis-ANS of different concentrations and were equilibrated for 20 h. Fluorescence intensity at 490 nm was measured taking both the excitation and emission slits of 2.5 nm. In this case also, the reverse titration was done as before. In case of equilibrium incubation, for pre-heated α_L -crystallin, 0.1 mg/ml α_L -crystallin was heated at 90 °C for 30 min and cooled for 1 h. After cooling, separate solutions of α_L -crystallin were equilibrated for 20 h with bis-ANS varying the concentration from 0–45 μ M.

To study the effect of time dependence on bis-ANS binding of pre-heated α_L -crystallin, 0.1 mg/ml α_L -crystallin was incubated at 90 °C for 30 min and after cooling for 30 min aliquots were mixed with bis-ANS of various concentrations. After incubation of 30 min with bis-ANS, fluorescence intensity at 490 nm was measured for each solution. The time of cooling in this case was 1 h. Then after different time interval (up to 24 h) readings were recorded for each solution.

Thermal unfolding and refolding measurements :

α_L -Crystallin solution of 0.1 mg/ml was incubated with bis-ANS (final concentration 20 μ M) in the fluorescence cuvette placed in a thermostatted cell holder in the spectrofluorimeter. The cell holder was maintained at constant temperature by circulating water from a constant temperature water bath. The sample

was equilibrated for 5 min at each temperature ranging from 25–90 °C before emission spectra were measured. From the bis-ANS fluorescence spectra, fluorescence intensity at 490 nm as well as wavelength maxima (λ_{\max}) were recorded.

Refolding experiments were done in two ways. In one case, the sample that was heated to 90 °C, was gradually cooled and during cooling, bis-ANS fluorescence spectra were recorded at various receding temperature. In another case, two sets of experiments were done where separate solutions were first heated to respective temperatures for 30 min and then cooled back to 25 °C for 1 h. In one set, bis-ANS was added to α_L -crystallin solution before heating and in another set bis-ANS was added to the solutions which were cooled to 25 °C after heating to respective temperatures. The similar experiment was performed with ANS instead of bis-ANS where the final concentration of ANS was 50 μ M.

Assay of chaperone activity :

(a) DTT-induced aggregation of insulin :

Chaperone activity of both bis-ANS and ANS-bound α A- and α B-crystallin was measured using insulin as a substrate¹⁷. The prevention of aggregation of reduced insulin B-chain by bound and unbound α A- and α B-crystallin was monitored by measuring the apparent absorbance at 450 nm as a function of time. For the assay, α A- and α B-crystallin were incubated at 37 °C with and without bis-ANS and ANS for 16 h. 0.35 mg/ml insulin in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 was reduced with 20 mM freshly prepared DTT in a cuvette kept at 37 °C in thermostatted cell holder of Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometer in the absence or presence of α A- and α B-crystallin. Probe-incubated α A-crystallin was added to insulin solution and incubated at 37 °C for 30 min in cuvette. Then DTT solution was added to a final concentration of 20 mM. In the assay mixture, concentration of α A-crystallin was 0.7 mg/ml, bis-ANS was of 50 μ M and ANS was of 100 μ M. α A-Crystallin without probe was also used for the assay

at 37 °C. For α B-crystallin, assay mixture contained insulin, 0.35 mg/ml; α B-crystallin, 0.175 mg/ml; bis-ANS, 12.5 μ M; ANS, 25 μ M and DTT, 20 mM.

(b) Heat-induced aggregation of β_L -crystallin :

β_L -Crystallin of 0.2 mg/ml in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer containing 0.1 M NaCl, pH 7.2 was taken in a cuvette and kept at 55 °C in thermostatted cell holder in the spectrophotometer. The aggregation of β_L -crystallin was monitored by measuring apparent absorbance at 450 nm against time¹². α A- and α B-Crystallin were incubated at 55 °C with and without bis-ANS for 1 h. For assay, at first, calculated amount of buffer was taken in cuvette and kept at 55 °C for 5 min. Bis-ANS incubated α A-crystallin was added to it and kept for another 5 min for equilibration. Then β_L -crystallin was added to the reaction mixture and protection of aggregation was monitored at 55 °C in the spectrophotometer. The prevention of aggregation was also monitored with α A-crystallin pre-incubated at 55 °C. Assay mixture contained β_L -crystallin, 0.2 mg/ml; α A-crystallin, 0.025 mg/ml and bis-ANS, 10 μ M. For α B-crystallin, the concentrations were same as α A-crystallin.

Results and discussion

Bis-ANS is a fluorescent dye and it is widely used as a probe to determine surface exposure of hydrophobic sites and conformational changes in proteins^{25,33–36}. The fluorescence intensity of bis-ANS in aqueous environment was very low showing emission maximum at around 540 nm. But fluorescence of bis-ANS markedly increased after binding to hydrophobic sites of proteins³⁷. The increase in fluorescence intensity of bis-ANS between 38 and 50 °C indicated the exposure of additional hydrophobic sites on the surface of the α_L -crystallin. An irreversible conformational change occurred beyond 50 °C leading to marked increase exposed hydrophobicity²⁵. To characterize the hydrophobic sites of α_L -crystallin, we measured emission maximum (λ_{\max}) of the heat-treated samples. With increase of temperature from 25–90 °C, λ_{\max} gradually increased from 479 nm to

Fig. 1. Emission wavelength maxima of bis-ANS during thermal unfolding (open square) and subsequent refolding (solid circle) of α_L -crystallin as a function of temperature. Protein concentration was 0.1 mg/ml and bis-ANS concentration was 20 μ M.

511 nm as shown in Fig. 1. It was interesting to see that, during the cycle of cooling from 90–25 °C, α_L -crystallin refolded in such a way that λ_{max} was almost similar at the respective temperature during the heating cycle. Thus the intensity profiles during heating and cooling showed irreversibility, but emission maximum were apparently reversible.

In order to gain further insight into the nature of exposure of hydrophobic sites of α_L -crystallin, we performed the bis-ANS binding experiment in two ways. In the first case, α_L -crystallin and bis-ANS were incubated at each temperature between 25 and 75 °C and then cooled back to 25 °C. In the second case, α_L -crystallin without bis-ANS was incubated at each temperature and bis-ANS was added only after cooling to 25 °C. In both cases fluorescence intensity and corresponding λ_{max} were measured at 25 °C. The intensity profiles against pre-incubation temperature in both cases were shown in Fig. 2. It was found that in the first case (solutions heated with bis-ANS), intensity started to increase above 30 °C and tended to level off above 60 °C. In the second case (bis-

Fig. 2. Bis-ANS binding by α_L -crystallin pre-incubated at various temperatures and subsequently refolded on cooling to 25 °C. (Solid square) bis-ANS added before heating, (solid circle) bis-ANS added after heating and cooling. Protein concentration was 0.1 mg/ml and bis-ANS concentration was 20 μ M. Solutions equilibrated at each temperature for 30 min, then cooled to 25 °C for 1 h.

ANS added after cooling), increase in intensity was observed above 45 °C. The intensity at a given pre-incubation temperature was always higher in the first case. The data thus indicated that some hydrophobic pockets which opened up during heating were available to already present bis-ANS, but on cooling some of these sites closed down and were not available to bis-ANS added after cooling. The emission maxima in both cases remained constant (Fig. 3) around 478.5 nm which was indicative of fairly non-polar nature of the bis-ANS binding pockets. Thus although additional binding sites were exposed on pre-incubation, on cooling α_L -crystallin refolded in such a way that most of the hydrophobic pockets were well protected from aqueous environment.

We also used ANS instead of bis-ANS in the above experiments. In these cases also the difference in fluorescence intensity between the two cases of ANS added before and after heating was observed. But the difference in case of ANS was slightly lower than that in

Fig. 3. Emission wavelength maxima of bis-ANS, at 25 °C, as a function of denaturation temperature after refolding of α_L -crystallin. (Solid square) bis-ANS added before heating, (open triangle) bis-ANS added after heating and cooling. Protein concentration was 0.1 mg/ml and bis-ANS concentration was 20 μ M. Solutions incubated at each temperature for 30 min, then cooled to 25 °C for 1 h.

Fig. 4. Fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) of ANS, at 25 °C, as a function of denaturation temperature after refolding of α_L -crystallin. (Solid square) ANS added before heating, (solid circle) ANS added after heating and cooling. Protein concentration was 0.1 mg/ml and ANS concentration was 50 μ M. Solutions equilibrated at each temperature for 30 min, then cooled to 25 °C for 1 h.

case of bis-ANS as shown in Fig. 4. This indicated that since ANS is smaller in size than bis-ANS (bis-ANS is dimer of ANS) it can easily access those hydrophobic sites that are not accessible for bis-ANS. The wavelength maxima for refolded α_L -crystallin in both the cases were same (Fig. 5) indicating no changes in the polarity of the sites of binding.

Number of binding sites for hydrophobic probes in α_L -crystallin is a matter of debate. While some people reported about 40 ANS binding sites per native α_L -crystallin³⁸, others reported one ANS binding site per 24 subunits of α_L -crystallin³⁹. It was also reported that there was one bis-ANS binding site per α_L -crystallin subunit⁴⁰. We determined the number of binding site (n) and dissociation constant (K_d) of bovine α_L -crystallin and recombinant human α_A - and α_B -crystallin for native and pre-heated state from the fluorescence titration data by Scatchard analysis. The profile of titration of α_L -crystallin by bis-ANS was

shown in Fig. 6(A). The bis-ANS binding was also studied in another way by allowing bis-ANS of various concentrations to equilibrate in presence of α_L -crystallin by 20 h incubation. The intensity profile as a function of bis-ANS concentration was shown in Fig. 6(B).

Earlier reports showed that interaction of ANS or bis-ANS with α -crystallin depended on temperature^{24,25,27,41}. It was also reported that prior heat treatment of α -crystallin at 70 °C resulted in increase in the number of binding sites⁴⁰. Fig. 7(A) showed fluorescence titration curve and Fig. 7(B) showed the equilibrium incubation data for bis-ANS binding by heat pre-treated α_L -crystallin. All the bis-ANS binding data were analyzed by the Scatchard equation (insets of Fig. 6(A,B) and Fig. 7(A,B)) and the results were shown in Table 1. For native α_L -crystallin, fluorimetric titration yielded the number of binding sites as 0.25, which is one bis-ANS per 4 subunits of α_L -

Fig. 5. Emission wavelength maxima of ANS, at 25 °C, as a function of denaturation temperature after refolding of α_L -crystallin. (Solid square) ANS added before heating, (open triangle) ANS added after heating and cooling. Protein concentration was 0.1 mg/ml and ANS concentration was 50 μ M. Solutions incubated at each temperature for 30 min, then cooled to 25 °C for 1 h.

crystallin. The affinity was about 2 μ M. When the binding was studied by equilibrium incubation method, both high and low affinity binding was observed. Low affinity binding corresponded to $n = 0.58$ with $K_d = 4 \mu$ M while higher affinity sites corresponded to $n = 0.31$ and $K_d = 0.34 \mu$ M. On pre-incubation of α_L -crystallin, fluorimetric titration yielded $n = 0.53$ with $K_d = 2.8 \mu$ M. Thus there was a two-fold increase in number of binding sites on pre-heating leading to one bis-ANS binding per 2 subunits of α_L -crystallin. When the binding of pre-heated α_L -crystallin was studied by equilibrium incubation method, low affinity site with $n = 0.64$ and $K_d = 2.9 \mu$ M and high affinity site with $n = 0.31$ and $K_d = 0.26 \mu$ M were observed. Interestingly, the high affinity binding site in both native and pre-heated α_L -crystallin had very similar characteristics. The number of low affinity binding site was slightly increased due to heat pre-treatment and the binding affinity was also slightly enhanced (Table 1).

Fig. 6. Bis-ANS binding by native α_L -crystallin at 25 °C. (A) Fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) by titration, (B) fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) by equilibrium incubation. Inset : Scatchard plot for the binding of bis-ANS to α_L -crystallin. α_L -Crystallin concentration was 0.1 mg/ml.

In order to study the bis-ANS binding of individual subunits of αA - and αB -crystallin, we performed bis-ANS titration of native and pre-heated recombinant αA - and αB -crystallin. The heat pre-treatment was done at 25 °C, 37 °C and 55 °C. The Scatchard analysis of the titration data were presented in Table 2. It was seen that with increase in pre-incubation temperature, the number of hydrophobic sites increased in case of αA -crystallin and decreased in case of αB -crystallin (Table 2). It was also observed that the number of hydrophobic sites were greater in case of αB -crystallin than in αA -crystallin at each pre-incubation temperature. This data is in agreement with the previous result which showed higher hydrophobicity of αB - than αA -crystallin^{30,42,43}. These results also correlate with previous

Fig. 7. Bis-ANS binding by pre-heated (at 90 °C) α_L -crystallin. (A) Fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) by titration, (B) fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) by equilibrium incubation. Inset : Scatchard plot for the binding of bis-ANS to α_L -crystallin. α_L -Crystallin concentration was 0.1 mg/ml. Solutions equilibrated at 90 °C for 30 min, then cooled to 25 °C for 1 h.

Table 1. Calculation of number of binding site (n) and dissociation constant (K_d) of native and pre-heated α_L -crystallin

Method	Native α_L -crystallin		Pre-heated α_L -crystallin	
	n	K_d (mM)	n	K_d (mM)
Fluorimetric titration	0.25	1.95	0.53	2.80
Equilibrium incubation	0.58	4.0	0.64	2.91
	0.31	0.34	0.31	0.26

Table 2. Calculation of number of binding site (n) and dissociation constant (K_d) of αA - and αB -crystallin pre-heated at different temperature

Pre-incubation temp. (°C)	αA -Crystallin		αB -Crystallin	
	n	K_d (mM)	n	K_d (mM)
25	0.19	1.27	0.55	2.59
37	0.19	1.31	0.44	1.90
55	0.28	1.28	0.38	1.53

results that showed chaperone properties of αA -crystallin improved, but that of αB -crystallin decreased with increase of temperature³⁰. K_d values were almost same in case of αA -crystallin but in case of αB -crystallin the value decreased with increase in pre-incubation temperature. This indicated that although the number of hydrophobic sites increased with increase in temperature, the affinity of binding was same in case of αA -crystallin. But in case of αB -crystallin, the number of hydrophobic sites decreased with increase in temperature but the affinity of binding increased meaning that pre-incubation at 55 °C led to tighter binding of bis-ANS.

It was shown that once exposed to the elevated temperature, α_L -crystallin upon cooling did not return to its original conformational state but returned to a conformation with markedly enhanced surface hydrophobicity. To further understand the reasons for this irreversibility, we have performed another experiment where prior heat-treated α_L -crystallin was incubated with different concentrations of bis-ANS. The measurement of fluorescence intensity at 490 nm of each solution after various time ranging from 1 h to 24 h as a function of bis-ANS concentration revealed that the enhancement of hydrophobic sites did not depend on time (Fig. 8). The exposure of hydrophobic sites which occur within 1 h, that was also same after incubation for 24 h. So there was no slow kinetics occurring after addition of bis-ANS. The relatively high fluorescence level of pre-heated sample remained essentially unchanged upon the incubation at room temperature for at least 48 h (data not shown).

The chaperone activity of ANS or bis-ANS bound and unbound αA -crystallin as assayed by insulin aggregation, was presented in Fig. 9(A). The corresponding results for αB -crystallin were presented in Fig. 9(B). ANS-bound and unbound αA -crystallin showed almost similar protection (90%) against insulin aggregation at 37 °C at a ratio of 1 : 2 between insulin and αA -crystallin. But bis-ANS bound αA -crystallin showed lower protection at 37 °C. Like αA -crystallin, αB -crystallin also showed similar

Fig. 8. Bis-ANS fluorescence intensity (490 nm) of α_L -crystallin as a function of bis-ANS concentration varying time of cooling. α_L -Crystallin concentration was 0.1 mg/ml. Solutions equilibrated at 90 °C for 30 min and cooled for 30 min. The aliquots taken and different volume of bis-ANS added to each aliquot to maintain different concentration of bis-ANS. Fluorescence intensity recorded for each solution after 1 h (solid square), 3 h (open circle), 5 h (solid circle), 8 h (solid triangle) and 24 h (open square) from heating.

chaperone activity in presence and absence of ANS. On the other hand, the chaperone activity of α_B -crystallin significantly decreased at 37 °C when bound with bis-ANS. It was reported that bovine α -crystallin complexed with bis-ANS showed a partial loss in chaperone-like activity than native protein⁴⁰. Our insulin assay at 37 °C revealed that prior binding of bis-ANS to α_A - and α_B -crystallin slightly suppressed its chaperone activity (Fig. 9(A,B)). This indicated that substrate bound to the same hydrophobic sites where bis-ANS was bound. ANS is smaller in size than bis-ANS. Therefore its binding had a smaller effect.

In case of heat aggregation assay of α_L -crystallin at 55 °C, a different picture emerged. There was no change in chaperone activity between bis-ANS bound and unbound α_A - and α_B -crystallin (Fig. 10). At 55 °C, the hydrophobic pockets in α_A - and α_B -crystallin partially collapsed and so bis-ANS might partly come out from the hydrophobic sites at 55 °C. Be-

Fig. 9. DTT-induced aggregation of insulin B-chain at 37 °C in the absence and presence of (A) α_A -crystallin, (B) α_B -crystallin pre-incubated with bis-ANS and ANS at 37 °C for 16 h. (A) (1) No α_A -crystallin, (2) unbound α_A -crystallin pre-incubated at 37 °C, (3) α_A -crystallin with ANS pre-incubated at 37 °C and (4) α_A -crystallin with bis-ANS pre-incubated at 37 °C. (B) (1) No α_B -crystallin, (2) unbound α_B -crystallin pre-incubated at 37 °C, (3) α_B -crystallin with ANS pre-incubated at 37 °C and (4) α_B -crystallin with bis-ANS pre-incubated at 37 °C. Insulin concentration was 0.35 mg/ml, α_A -crystallin concentration 0.7 mg/ml and α_B -crystallin concentration 0.175 mg/ml.

cause of the flexible nature of binding between bis-ANS and α_A - or α_B -crystallin, the aggregation of β_L -crystallin at 55 °C was not affected by the presence of bis-ANS.

α -Crystallin is known to have significant amount of exposed surface hydrophobic sites that can bind to various hydrophobic probes such as ANS and bis-ANS. The exposed hydrophobic sites were also thought to be involved in the binding of target substrate proteins to α -crystallin during its chaperone activity^{14,30,44–46}. Several workers have shown a direct correlation between chaperone activity and exposed hydrophobicity of α -crystallin^{24,25,27,47–51}. It was also reported in the literature that temperature driven exposure of hydrophobic surfaces in α -crystallin was

Fig. 10. Heat-induced aggregation of β_L -crystallin at 55 °C in the absence and presence of (A) αA -crystallin, (B) αB -crystallin pre-incubated with bis-ANS at 55 °C for 1 h. (A) (1) No αA -crystallin, (2) unbound αA -crystallin pre-incubated at 55 °C, (3) αA -crystallin pre-incubated with bis-ANS at 55 °C. (B) (1) No αB -crystallin, (2) unbound αB -crystallin pre-incubated at 55 °C, (3) αB -crystallin pre-incubated with bis-ANS at 55 °C. β_L -Crystallin concentration was 0.2 mg/ml and both αA - and αB -crystallin concentration were 0.025 mg/ml.

accompanied by enhancement in chaperone activity^{25,30,46,52}. All these studies showed the importance of the use of hydrophobic probes for the understanding of the chaperone function of α -crystallin. We have used bis-ANS and ANS binding to understand some structural changes of thermally perturbed α -crystallin and get an insight into chaperone activity of thermally treated α -crystallin.

Structure of α -crystallin, though considered extremely stable⁴⁷, has been reported to melt above 60 °C^{30,42,53}. On cooling α -crystallin was believed to refold and the refolded protein showed the same far UVCD spectral characteristics⁴⁷. The refolded α_L -crystallin differed from native α_L -crystallin in their surface hydrophobic exposures²⁵. The environment of exposed hydrophobic groups during unfolding and refolding at the respective temperatures remained

unchanged (Fig. 1). Cooling of heated α_L -crystallin changed tertiary interactions resulting in loosely packed α_L -crystallin with native secondary structure. This loose structure allowed bis-ANS to bind to otherwise unavailable pockets. Decrease in fluorescence intensity when bis-ANS was added after cooling indicated that during cooling access to some hydrophobic pockets closed down (Fig. 2). It may be mentioned here that a very similar behaviour was observed for another protein β -lactoglobulin for the binding of ANS⁵⁴. Both α -crystallin and β -lactoglobulin are major β -sheet proteins with very little α -helical content. β -Lactoglobulin not only exhibited irreversible thermal refolding behaviour similar to the present result, but also showed cavity in refolded form. It is quite likely that such a cavity might form because of the increased difficulty of β -sheet structure to pack from a more random situation. The significant increase in bis-ANS intensity during cooling might be due to some trapping of free bis-ANS between β -sheet layers. The constancy of the emission maxima of bis-ANS bound to pre-incubated α_L -crystallin added before or after heating (Fig. 3) indicated that only number of exposed sites varied, but their environment remained unchanged. Experiment with ANS revealed the same picture (Figs. 4 and 5).

The other aspect of our study concerned quantitation of the number of hydrophobic binding sites in native and heat-treated α_L -crystallin and the affinity of the binding. We found that a relatively rapid titration method yielded one bis-ANS binding site for a native tetramer of α_L -crystallin but one bis-ANS binding site for heat-treated α_L -crystallin dimer. Increase in number of binding site for heat treated α_L -crystallin was accompanied by some loss in binding affinity (Table 1). High affinity binding sites were revealed when bis-ANS was allowed to equilibrate with α_L -crystallin. This showed that the bis-ANS binding process was a slow one. Initially bis-ANS bound to the pocket quite loosely and with time it was tightly grabbed into the pocket. This number of tight binding site was same for native and heat treated protein and their affinities were almost same. It was the low af-

finity binding site that increased in number with slightly enhanced affinity on pre-heat treatment. It was shown that pre-heat treatment improved chaperone activity of α_L -crystallin²⁵. The low affinity bis-ANS binding sites which reside on the surface of α_L -crystallin thus also interact with the substrate proteins increasing chaperone function.

The bis-ANS binding behaviour of individual subunits of αA - and αB -crystallin also revealed interesting features (Table 2). Differences in their structural, physico-chemical and chaperone function have been studied by various workers^{30,42,55}. It is already known that at room temperature, αB -crystallin was more hydrophobic than αA -crystallin^{30,42}. This feature was also observed in the present work at 25 °C (Table 2). Because of the higher hydrophobicity of αB -crystallin, it had a tendency to self aggregate at higher temperature⁵⁶ and hence 'n' decreased. However, the remaining pockets of αB -crystallin bound to bis-ANS with higher affinity as temperature increased. αA -Crystallin binding sites thermally exposed were of similar nature as K_d values were similar. Furthermore our results showed that although bis-ANS binding to α_L -crystallin was a relatively slow process and took few hours to reach equilibrium, the structural changes that occurred to α_L -crystallin on cooling a solution after heating above 60 °C was attained immediately (Fig. 8). The irreversibility therefore did not arise because of insufficient equilibration time, but was perhaps due to off-pathway intermediates trapped in the folding pathway. It was reported that hydrophobicity does not quantitatively correlate with the chaperone function of alpha-crystallins⁵⁷. A quantitative relationship between hydrophobicity and chaperone-like activity remains a matter to be concerned about.

Non-thermal chaperone activity assay of ANS or bis-ANS bound αA - or αB -crystallin showed lower activity than native αA - or αB -crystallin. This indicated that ANS or bis-ANS binding sites were responsible for interaction with the substrate proteins. Photoincorporation of bis-ANS into α -crystallin also showed similar reduction in chaperone activity^{36,58}.

Cross-linking studies also revealed that bis-ANS binding sites overlapped with substrate binding sites^{59,60}. However, our results indicate that ANS had very little effect on the chaperone function, but bis-ANS had a moderate effect. Bis-ANS is the dimer of ANS and acts as a bidentate ligand⁶¹. A substrate and ANS/bis-ANS competes for the same hydrophobic sites on α_L -crystallin. A substrate protein may easily replace a loosely bound ANS to interact with α_L -crystallin, but may not easily replace a bidentate bis-ANS bound to α_L -crystallin. At the condition of thermal assay, the interaction between ANS/bis-ANS and α_L -crystallin may be very flexible and hence presence of ANS or bis-ANS had very little effect on the chaperone activity of α_L -crystallin.

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